

MATHEMATICAL STUDY OF LAPLACE AND YOUNG EQUATIONS IN THE CASE OF THE CONTACT BETWEEN A DROP AND FIBRE

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SUMMARY : This paper constitutes a mathematical contribution on the theory of capillarity in a particular case of the contact of a drop on a cylindrical fibres, by giving a new formulation of the Laplace and Young equations in that case and proving the effect of the gravity force on the calculation of the contact angle of a drop on a fibre and the surface tension of the solid.. The mechanical equilibrium conditions which describe the state of balance across the separation surface or along the contact line were derived as force balance relations between pressure, surface tension and the geometric shape of the surface or the contact line; by using the classical method of the Lagrange multipliers and the variation theory. Our results are limited to capillary systems which are either in axisymmetric geometry or whose surfaces may be described by non-parametric surface function of the form $u = u(x,z)$. In many practical cases, the geometry of the solid is typically axisymmetric. A typical case of a axisymmetric solid, which was not mathematically very studied in literature, is that of a liquid drop in axisymmetric position in contact with a horizontal or vertical rigid cylindrical surface.

KEYWORDS : Fibre, contact angle, thermodynamics, Laplace and Young equations, drop, surface energy, Lagrange multipliers.

INTRODUCTION

Wetting of a solid surface by a liquid is of a vital importance in many industrial process, and more particularly the wettability of fibres presents a major interest in many industrial applications as drying and protection of synthetic fibres, textile industries, cosmetology industry and composite material elaboration. Many mathematical studies on the contact of a liquid on a plane solid surface or container surface [1-5]. However, we did not find any serious mathematical study with cylindrical surface, like a fibre.

We propose in this paper to study the mathematical modelling of the contact between an axisymmetric drop and cylindrical fibre in horizontal or vertical geometric position, by using the classical method of the Lagrange multipliers and the variation theory [5-7].

CASE OF A HORIZONTAL CYLINDRICAL FIBRE

In many practical cases, the geometry of the solid is typically axisymmetric. A typical case of an axisymmetric solid, very studied and commented in literature, is that of a container bounding a liquid - fluid system. Another case is that of a liquid drop in axisymmetric position in contact with a horizontal rigid cylindrical surface, where the contact line is generally a circle with a specific linear free energy, $\omega^{(l)}$, that is equal to a constant line tension, $\sigma_{\infty}^{(l)}$ (figure 1).

Fig. 1: Contact between a liquid drop and a cylindrical surface in axisymmetric equilibrium.

Where $u_i(r)$ is a surface curve separating between the liquid and the solid, $2u_s$ the length of the cylindrical surface having a diameter equal to $2a$. The liquid drop having an axisymmetric geometry intersects the r -axis in $\pm b$ and the u -axis in $\pm u_0$. We suppose that there is no chemical reaction between the liquid and the solid, and the contact angle of the wetting liquid is constant.

We previously showed [8] that the total energy is composed by contributions relative to different regions of bulk, and dividing surfaces and lines. The most important energetic contribution for the system is the intrinsic energy of bulk of every phase characterized by $\omega^{(v)} = -P$. Another form of energy present in the system is the gravitation potential energy that is function of the position into the system. The energetic contribution of the exterior field is obtained by integration over the total useful volume of the system including both liquid-fluid boundaries and the three phase contact lines.

Finally, if the quantity of the liquid present in the system is finite, we have to considerate its mass or its volume as a constraint introduced in this system. In the case where the system is incompressible, a method well-know and very used is that of the Lagrange multipliers, λ , which multiplies the volume V to form a new term of energy. According to the virtual work principle, the total free energy, E_f , has to be canceled for a certain variation that has not violate the constraints of the system. For an incompressible system, the volume constraint is unique. Two mechanical equilibrium conditions can be distinguished : the first condition is obtained along the liquid-fluid interface, $A^{(lf)}$ and the second one is realized along the three phase contact line.

Free energy of the drop

If $E^{(l)}$ is the free energy of the liquid phase and $\omega^{(l)}$ the specific free energy or the free energy density of the liquid, then $E^{(l)}$ can be expressed by the following integral (see figure 1) :

$$E^{(l)} = 4\pi \int_a^b |r| \int_0^{u_l(r)} \omega^{(l)} du dr \quad (1)$$

where $a \leq |r| \leq b$ et $0 \leq |u_l(r)| \leq u_0$

If we suppose that the contribution of the intrinsic internal energy of the bulk does not depend on that of the free energy of the external field, we can considerate that $\omega^{(l)}$ is independent from the u -coordinate, then a simple integration of (1) leads to :

$$E^{(l)} = 4\pi \int_a^b \omega^{(l)} u_l(r) r dr \quad (2)$$

Free energy of the fluid phase

The free energy $E^{(f)}$ of the fluid phase (gas or vapor in our study) will be given by :

$$E^{(f)} = 4\pi \int_0^a \omega^{(f)} [u_l(r) - u_s] r dr - 4\pi \int_0^b \omega^{(f)} u_l(r) r dr + 4\pi \int_0^{r_{\max}} \omega^{(f)} u_s r dr \quad (3)$$

where r_{\max} is the superior limit of the external boundary of the system.

Free energies of linear and surface regions

For solid-liquid interface :

$$E^{(sl)} = \iint_{A^{(sl)}} \omega^{(sl)} dA = 4\pi a \int_0^{u_0} \omega^{(sl)} du = 4\pi \int_0^a \frac{\omega^{(sl)} u_0}{a} a dr \quad (4)$$

For liquid-fluid interface

$$E^{(lf)} = \iint_{A^{(lf)}} \omega^{(lf)} dA = 4\pi \int_a^b \omega^{(lf)} \left[1 + \left(\frac{du_l}{dr} \right)^2 \right]^{\frac{1}{2}} r dr \quad (5)$$

For solid-fluid interface

$$E^{(sf)} = \iint_{A^{(sf)}} \omega^{(sf)} dA = 4\pi a \int_{u_0}^{u_s} \omega^{(sf)} du = 4\pi \int_0^a \frac{\omega^{(sf)} (u_s - u_0)}{a} a dr \quad (6)$$

and for the contact line, we have :

$$E^{(slf)} = 4\pi \int_0^a \frac{\omega^{(slf)}}{a} a dr \quad (7)$$

The expressions of liquid phase $V^{(l)}$ and fluid phase $V^{(f)}$ volumes are respectively given by :

$$V^{(f)} = 4\pi \int_a^b (u_0 - u_l(r)) r dr + 4\pi \int_b^{r_{\max}} u_0 r dr + 4\pi \int_a^{r_{\max}} (u_s - u_0) r dr \quad (8)$$

Effect of the exterior forces

The same types of previous expressions were obtained with the action of the gravitation field. As example, we give $E_{gravit.}^{(l)}$, corresponding to the contribution of the gravity of the liquid drop, is given by :

$$E_{gravit.}^{(l)} = 4\pi \int_a^b g r^2 \int_0^{u_l(r)} \rho^{(l)} du dr = 4\pi \int_a^b \rho^{(l)} g r u_l(r) r dr \quad (9)$$

where $\rho^{(l)}$ is the bulk density of the liquid phase.

Study of the variational problem

The total free energy of the system is given by :

$$E_t = E^{(l)} + E^{(f)} + E^{(lf)} + E^{(sl)} + E^{(sf)} + E^{(sfl)} \\ + E_{gravit.}^{(l)} + E_{gravit.}^{(f)} + E_{gravit.}^{(sl)} + E_{gravit.}^{(lf)} + E_{gravit.}^{(sf)} + E_{gravit.}^{(sfl)} \quad (10)$$

The mechanical equilibrium conditions will be obtained by using the fact that the integral of the total free energy is constant. The variational problem can be written here as :

$$\delta [E_t + \lambda V^{(l)}] = 0 \quad (11)$$

with

$$V^{(l)} = 4\pi \int_a^b u_l(r) r dr$$

where λ is the Lagrange multiplier. The problem (11) can be also written as :

$$\delta \left[\int_0^a F_1 r dr + \int_0^a F_2 r dr + \int_0^b F_3 r dr + \int_0^{r_{max}} F_4 r dr \right] = 0 \quad (12)$$

where F_1 and F_2 depend on r , $u_l(r)$ and $u'_l(r)$: $F_1 = F_1(r, u_l, u'_l)$ et $F_2 = F_2(r, u_l, u'_l)$

If we apply the variational calculus to the first integral, we obtain :

$$\frac{\partial(F_1 r)}{\partial u_l} - \frac{d}{dr} \left[\frac{\partial(F_1 r)}{\partial u'_l} \right] = 0 \quad (13)$$

we obtain :

$$\left(\omega^{(lf)} + \rho^{(f)} g r \right) \left[\frac{1}{R_1^{(lf)}} + \frac{1}{R_2^{(lf)}} \right] + \rho^{(f)} g \frac{r}{R_1^{(lf)}} + \left(\omega^{(f)} - \omega^{(l)} \right) + \left(\rho^{(f)} - \rho^{(l)} \right) g r - \lambda = 0 \quad (14)$$

Where the principal radii of curvature of the liquid-fluid interface are given by :

$$\frac{1}{R_1^{(lf)}} = \frac{u'_l}{r(1+u_l'^2)^{1/2}} \quad \text{and} \quad \frac{1}{R_2^{(lf)}} = \frac{u_l''}{(1+u_l'^2)^{3/2}} \quad (15)$$

The boundary conditions in $r = b$ allow to obtain the Laplace equation :

Laplace equation

Calculations lead to Laplace equation :

$$w^{(lf)}(r) \left[\frac{1}{R_1^{(lf)}(r)} + \frac{1}{R_2^{(lf)}(r)} \right] = \Delta P_0^{(lf)}(r) \quad (16)$$

The pressure variation is given by :

$$\Delta P_0^{(lf)}(r) = g(r-b)\Delta\rho + \rho^{(f)} g \left[2 - \frac{r}{R_1^{(lf)}} \right] + \frac{\omega^{(f)}}{b} \quad (17)$$

and

$$w^{(lf)}(r) = \left(\omega^{(lf)} + \rho^{(f)} g r \right) \quad (18)$$

Equation (16) represents the *Laplace equation* in the case of a liquid drop in axisymmetric geometry on a horizontal cylindrical fiber.

Young equation

The transversality condition applied at the three phase contact point $r = a$, allows to obtain the Young equation.

$$w^{(lf)}(a) \left[-\frac{\cos \theta_L}{a} + \frac{\sin \theta_L}{u_0} + u_1''(a) \sin^3 \theta_L \right] - \rho^{(lf)} g \cos \theta_L = \frac{w^{(sl)}(a) - w^{(sf)}(a)}{a} + \frac{w^{(slf)}(a)}{u_0 a} \quad (19)$$

where $w^i(a) = (\omega^{(i)} + \rho^{(i)} g a)$ where $(i) \in \{(lf), (sf), (sl), (slf), (f)\}$

Equation (19) represents *the generalized Young equation* in the case of a drop surrounding a horizontal cylindrical surface.

Particular cases

1- If the effect of the gravitation is neglected, then equation (19) becomes :

$$\omega^{(lf)} \left[\frac{\cos \theta_L}{a} - \frac{\sin \theta_L}{u_0} - u_1''(a) \sin^3 \theta_L \right] = \frac{\omega^{(sf)} - \omega^{(sl)}}{a} - \frac{\omega^{(slf)}}{u_0 a} \quad (20)$$

2- Furthermore, if we suppose that the solid surface is plane, $a \rightarrow \infty$, we obtain :

$$\cos \theta_L = \frac{\omega^{(sf)} - \omega^{(sl)}}{\omega^{(lf)}} - \frac{\omega^{(slf)}}{u_0 \omega^{(lf)}} \quad (21)$$

3- If we neglect the three phase tension line, then equation (21) becomes:

$$\cos \theta_L = \frac{\omega^{(sf)} - \omega^{(sl)}}{\omega^{(lf)}} \quad (22)$$

Equation (22) is exactly the classical Young equation.

CASE OF A VERTICAL CYLINDRICAL FIBRE

If the position of the previous cylindrical surface is vertical, we obtain the following results :

Laplace equation

$$w^{(lf)}(u_1(r)) \left[\frac{1}{R_1^{(lf)}(r)} + \frac{1}{R_2^{(lf)}(r)} \right] = \Delta P_0^{(lf)}(r) \quad (23)$$

$$\Delta P_0^{(lf)}(r) = \rho^{(lf)} g \frac{r}{R_1^{(lf)} u_1'} + (\rho^{(l)} - \rho^{(f)}) g u_1 + \frac{\omega^{(lf)}}{b} \quad (24)$$

Equation de Young

Transversality condition leads to :

$$w^{(lf)}(u_0) \left[-\frac{\cos \theta_L}{a} + \frac{\sin \theta_L}{u_0} + u_1''(a) \sin^3 \theta_L \right] - \rho^{(lf)} g \sin \theta_L = \frac{\rho^{(l)} - \rho^{(f)}}{2} g u_0 + \frac{w^{(sl)}(a) - w^{(sf)}(a)}{a} + \frac{w^{(slf)}(a)}{u_0 a} \quad (25)$$

Particular cases

1- If the effect of the gravitation of the contact surfaces and lines is neglected, we will have :

$$\omega^{(lf)} \left[\frac{\cos \theta_L}{a} - \frac{\sin \theta_L}{u_0} - u_i''(a) \sin^3 \theta_L \right] = \frac{\rho^{(f)} - \rho^{(l)}}{2} g u_0 + \frac{\omega^{(sf)} - \omega^{(sl)}}{a} - \frac{\omega^{(slf)}}{u_0 a} \quad (26)$$

2- In the case of plane surface, we obtain :

$$\cos \theta_L = \frac{\omega^{(sf)} - \omega^{(sl)}}{\omega^{(lf)}} + \frac{\rho^{(f)} - \rho^{(l)}}{2} a g u_0 - \frac{\omega^{(slf)}}{u_0 \omega^{(lf)}} \quad (27)$$

3- If we neglect the three phase tension line, we obtain :

$$\cos \theta_L = \frac{\omega^{(sf)} - \omega^{(sl)}}{\omega^{(lf)}} + \frac{\rho^{(f)} - \rho^{(l)}}{2} a g u_0 \quad (28)$$

If we compare the two cases of horizontal and vertical cylindrical surfaces, we observe that in the second case (vertical one) there is an important influence of the gravitation of the liquid and of the solid on the contact angle of the drop on the solid.

EQUILIBRIUM OF A SOLID-LIQUID 1-LIQUID 2-FLUID SYSTEM

Another case was studied is that of the contact gaz-liquid1-liquid2-cylindrical surface (Fig. 2). Three surfaces can be distinguished : solid, liquid 1 (l) and liquid 2 (h) (oil, for example) in presence of a fluid (f) (gas). We also distinguish between four surface interfaces : solid-fluid (sf), solid-liquid (sl), liquid-oil (lh) and oil-fluid (hf), and two contact lines : solid-liquid-fluid (slf) and liquid-oil-fluid (lhf). We studied the case where oil and liquid are in contact with the fibre. Liquid surface are characterized by $u_l(r)$ and oil surface by $v_h(r)$.

Fig. 2. Contact between, liquid 1, liquid 2 (oil) and cylindrical fibre

Variational problem

The total free energy is given by the following expression :

$$\begin{aligned} E_t = & E^{(l)} + E^{(h)} + E^{(f)} + E^{(sh)} + E^{(sl)} + E^{(sf)} + E^{(lh)} + E^{(hf)} + E^{(slh)} + E^{(shf)} + E_{gravit.}^{(l)} \\ & + E_{gravit.}^{(h)} + E_{gravit.}^{(f)} + E_{gravit.}^{(sl)} + E_{gravit.}^{(sh)} + E_{gravit.}^{(sf)} + E_{gravit.}^{(lh)} + E_{gravit.}^{(hf)} + E_{gravit.}^{(slh)} + E_{gravit.}^{(shf)}. \end{aligned} \quad (29)$$

The variational problem will be written as :

$$\delta [E_t + \lambda_1 V^{(l)} + \lambda_2 V^{(h)}] = 0 \quad (30)$$

Calculations give :

$$\delta \left[\int_0^a F_1 r dr + \int_0^a F_2 r dr + \int_0^b F_3 r dr + \int_0^c F_4 r dr + \int_0^c F_5 r dr + \int_0^{r_{\max}} F_6 r dr \right] = 0 \quad (31)$$

with

$$\begin{aligned} F_1(r, u, u') = & [w^{(h)}(r) - w^{(l)}(r) - \lambda_1 + \lambda_2] u_l(r) - w^{(lf)}(r) [1 + (u_l'(r))^2]^{\frac{1}{2}} \\ & + \frac{w^{(slh)}(a)}{a} + [w^{(sl)}(a) - w^{(sh)}(a)] \frac{u_0}{a} \end{aligned} \quad (32)$$

$$\begin{aligned} F_2(r, v, v') = & [w^{(f)}(r) - w^{(h)}(r) + \lambda_2] v_h(r) - w^{(hf)}(r) [1 + (v_h'(r))^2]^{\frac{1}{2}} \\ & + \frac{w^{(shf)}(a)}{a} + [w^{(sh)}(a) - w^{(sf)}(a)] \frac{v_0}{a} \end{aligned} \quad (33)$$

$$F_3(r, u, u') = [w^{(l)}(r) + \lambda_1] [u_0 - u_l(r)] + w^{(lh)}(r) [1 + (u_l'(r))^2]^{\frac{1}{2}} \quad (34)$$

$$F_4(r, v, v') = [w^{(h)}(r) + w^{(f)}(r) + \lambda_2] v_h(r) - v_0 w^{(f)}(r) + w^{(hf)}(r) [1 + (v_h'(r))^2]^{\frac{1}{2}} \quad (35)$$

$$F_5(r, u) = -[w^{(h)}(r) + \lambda_2] u_l(r) \quad (36)$$

$$F_6(r) = w^{(f)}(r) u_s \quad (37)$$

The boundary conditions are given by :

$$u_l(r=a) = u_0 \text{ et } u_l(r=b) = 0, \quad u_l'(b) = \infty \text{ ou } \frac{1}{u_l'(b)} = 0. \quad (38)$$

$$v_h(r=a) = u_1(r=a) = v_0 \text{ et } v_h(r=c) = 0, \quad v_h'(c) = \infty \text{ ou } \frac{1}{v_h'(c)} = 0. \quad (39)$$

Variational calculus applied respectively to $F_1 r$, $F_2 r$ and to $F_3 r$ allow to obtain :

$$w^{(lh)}(r) \left[\frac{1}{R_1^{(lh)}} + \frac{1}{R_2^{(lh)}} \right] + \rho^{(lh)} g \frac{r}{R_1^{(lh)}} + w^{(h)}(r) - w^{(l)}(r) - \lambda_1 + \lambda_2 = 0 \quad (40)$$

$$w^{(hf)}(r) \left[\frac{1}{R_1^{(hf)}} + \frac{1}{R_2^{(hf)}} \right] + \rho^{(hf)} g \frac{r}{R_1^{(hf)}} + w^{(f)}(r) - w^{(h)}(r) - \lambda_2 = 0 \quad (42)$$

$$w^{(lh)}(r) \left[\frac{1}{R_1^{(lh)}} + \frac{1}{R_2^{(lh)}} \right] + \rho^{(lh)} g \frac{r}{R_1^{(lh)}} - w^{(l)}(r) - \lambda_1 = 0 \quad (43)$$

Laplace equations

Applying the boundary conditions in $r = c$ and $r = b$ respectively to the equations (42) and (43), we obtain :

$$\lambda_1 = \left[\frac{w^{(lh)}(b)}{b} + \rho^{(lh)}g - w^{(l)}(b) \right] \quad (44)$$

$$\lambda_2 = \left[\frac{w^{(hf)}(c)}{c} + \rho^{(hf)}g + w^{(f)}(c) - w^{(h)}(c) \right] \quad (45)$$

and Laplace equations will be given by :

$$w^{(lh)}(r) \left[\frac{1}{R_1^{(lh)}(r)} + \frac{1}{R_2^{(lh)}(r)} \right] = \Delta P_0^{(lh)}(r) \quad (46)$$

$$w^{(hf)}(r) \left[\frac{1}{R_1^{(hf)}(r)} + \frac{1}{R_2^{(hf)}(r)} \right] = \Delta P_0^{(hf)}(r) \quad (47)$$

where

$$\Delta P_0^{(lh)}(r) = \rho^{(lh)}g \left[2 - \frac{r}{R_1^{(lh)}} \right] - \rho^{(l)}(b-r) + \frac{\omega^{(lh)}}{b} \quad (48)$$

$$\Delta P_0^{(hf)}(r) = \rho^{(hf)}g \left[2 - \frac{r}{R_1^{(hf)}} \right] + (\rho^{(f)} - \rho^{(h)})(c-r) + \frac{\omega^{(hf)}}{c} \quad (49)$$

Young equations

Using the following transversality conditions

$$\begin{cases} (F_1 r) - u'_1 \left(\frac{\partial(F_1 r)}{\partial u'_1} \right) = 0 & \text{en } r = a \\ (F_2 r) - u'_1 \left(\frac{\partial(F_2 r)}{\partial u'_1} \right) = 0 & \text{en } r = a \end{cases} \quad (50)$$

we obtain the first Young equation

$$\begin{aligned} w^{(lf)}(a) \left[-\frac{\cos \theta_L}{a} + \frac{\sin \theta_L}{u_0} + u'_1''(a) \sin^3 \theta_L \right] - \rho^{(lf)}g \cos \theta_L \\ = \frac{w^{(sl)}(a) - w^{(sf)}(a)}{a} + \frac{w^{(slf)}(a)}{u_0 a} \end{aligned} \quad (51)$$

and the second Young equation :

$$\begin{aligned} w^{(hf)}(a) \left[-\frac{\cos \theta_H}{a} + \frac{\sin \theta_H}{v_0} + v'_1''(a) \sin^3 \theta_H \right] - \rho^{(hf)}g \cos \theta_H \\ = \frac{w^{(sh)}(a) - w^{(sf)}(a)}{a} + \frac{w^{(shf)}(a)}{v_0 a} \end{aligned} \quad (52)$$

where θ_H is the contact angle of the oil drop with the fibre.

Particular cases

1- In the case of a plane surface, we have :

$$\cos \theta_L = \frac{\omega^{(sf)} - \omega^{(sl)}}{\omega^{(lf)}} - \frac{\omega^{(stf)}}{u_0 \omega^{(lf)}} \quad (53)$$

$$\cos \theta_H = \frac{\omega^{(sf)} - \omega^{(sh)}}{\omega^{(hf)}} - \frac{\omega^{(shf)}}{v_0 \omega^{(hf)}} \quad (54)$$

2- If $u_0 = v_0$, i.e., the two three phase tension lines (slh) and (shf) are the same, the angle β between the two interfaces liquid-oil and oil-fluid in the point (a, u_0) will be given by $\beta = \theta_H - \theta_L$.

CONCLUSIONS

In this study, we gave a new mathematical formulation of the Laplace and Young equations in the three following cases :

- 1- contact between a liquid drop and a horizontal cylindrical surface
- 2- contact of the drop with a vertical cylindrical surface
- 3- contact between two liquids and horizontal cylindrical surface.

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